

REFLECTION ON EU INSTRUMENTS AND THE GREEN DEAL: STRATEGIC ADAPTATION OR RETREAT?

BRIEFING NOTE

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The European Commission's recent "omnibus" proposals introduce major regulatory changes that collectively affect the operational impact of the European Green Deal. Across policy areas, the response of the EU institutions is signalling a recalibration of expectations: climate and environmental objectives remain formally endorsed but are increasingly subordinated to competitiveness, security, and short-term cost relief, with growing implications for transparency and accountability.

The **Sustainability Omnibus** (CSRD, CSDDD, Taxonomy, CBAM) narrows the scope of corporate sustainability rules, limits due diligence obligations, and weakens key accountability mechanisms. Together with the parallel "simplification" of related instruments—such as the EU Deforestation Regulation—, these changes reduce documentation and control points along supply chains, thereby lowering the baseline against which delivery of the Green Deal is assessed. **The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Omnibus**—driven by the perceived need to respond to sustained farmer mobilization—relaxes environmental conditionalities (GAEC), eases controls and penalties for smaller farms, and expands administrative flexibility for EU Member States. Similar patterns can be observed in the proposals for several other EU omnibus packages: the investment omnibus proposes increased flexibility in reporting and compliance obligations and weaker traceability; the defence omnibus creates further exemptions from environmental and chemical rules; and the chemicals and digital packages include delays in hazard communication—such as postponing the disclosure of chemical risks, toxicity data, or safety-related information to users—or weaker data transparency.

The positions taken by the Council of Ministers largely align with the Commission's deregulatory direction, while the European Parliament shows increasing internal contradictions as it supports long-term climate targets while also backing simplification measures that undermine the implementation tools necessary to achieve said targets.

Threats to the overall sustainability agenda can be identified at two levels: substantive opacity and procedural shortcuts. The former arises from the bundling of multiple changes into a single act, which obscures the true impact of the policies. This is compounded by procedural bypass mechanisms, where acts are adopted through accelerated timelines, limited stakeholder involvement, and minimal impact assessments. **Together, these aspects create a situation in which the EU's green transition becomes more difficult to monitor, scrutinize, and effectively implement.**

Overall, while the omnibus packages as proposed and partially endorsed do not repeal the European Green Deal, they contribute to a “quiet downgrading” of its functioning and operational force. Bundled amendments, accelerated procedures, and lighter reporting create changes to the regulatory baseline and complicate the verification of whether “green” budgets produce real outcomes. Building on the conclusions of the [previous briefing](#) published by SLYCAN Trust, the combined effect of the deregulatory omnibus packages and shifting budgetary priorities points toward a “Fragmented Scenario” as outlined in said publication. **In this scenario, the Green Deal remains present in the political rhetoric and as a cross-cutting label but increasingly lacks the enforceable obligations, clear spending envelopes and robust accountability mechanisms needed for effective delivery.**

I. Purpose and angle

This briefing note takes the European Commission's recent substantive "omnibus" packages as the starting point – in particular, the 2025 Omnibus Simplification Package on sustainability and corporate rules, the Omnibus reforming the InvestEU Regulation and other funding instruments, the agricultural Omnibus packages on Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) simplification, and the simplification omnibus proposal on chemicals¹.

The briefing then works back to assess how these omnibus packages link to the evolving EU budget architecture and their possible implications for the future of the European Green Deal. The brief also tries—building on the narrative developed in our recently published budgetary brief—to analyse how the packages link to the EU's shifting political priorities as well as the growing risks for transparency and accountability around green and just transition finance. Across policy areas, the European Commission as well as the Council of Ministers and the European Parliament (EP) as co-legislators, are signalling a recalibration of expectations: **green objectives are increasingly subordinated to competitiveness, security, and short-term cost relief**. Therefore, the main questions to be asked and answered are: What does this imply for the future of the European Green Deal? Is it still central to EU policymaking or do the EU's public announcements increasingly sound hollow?

The Green Deal was presented in 2019 as the EU's answer to the growing concerns over the threats to the survival of the European model and as an answer to the challenges of the triple environmental crisis of climate change, biodiversity loss, and pollution. It was introduced in response to and supported by the demands of a concerned public—in particular, the younger generation—for a greener and more sustainable Europe. Furthermore, it was presented as a comprehensive plan to support and enable a transition of the European economy toward climate neutrality. The EU's Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) for 2021-2027 also reflected that, but as our previous [policy briefing](#)² has outlined, the EU's budgetary (and recently also policy) priorities, influenced by a changed economic and geopolitical environment, underwent a notable shift even before the elections for the EP and the establishment of a new College of Commissioners in 2024. **This shift, driven and reinforced by EU Member States (MS), has raised questions about the Union's willingness and ability to deliver on the commitments made at the start of the decade.**

This paper examines recent policy developments within the EU to assess whether its legal and financial instruments – and, by extension, its political direction – continue to align with the Green Deal's core objectives, including reducing emissions by at least 55% by 2030 and achieving climate neutrality by 2050 under the European Climate Law.

1. Omnibus I Proposal for a Directive amending multiple sustainability-related directives COM(2025) 81 final, Omnibus II Proposal for a Regulation amending several financial-services legislative acts (investment simplification) COM(2025) 82 final, Omnibus III Proposal amending the conditionality system, types of intervention in the form of direct payment, types of intervention in certain sectors and rural development and annual performance reports (...) COM(2025) 203 final, Omnibus IV Proposal for a Regulation amending product-safety, standardisation and SME-related legislation COM(2025) 315 final, Omnibus V Proposal for a Defence package simplifying EU defence-industry regulatory procedures COM(2025) 402 final, Omnibus VI Proposal for a Regulation simplifying chemicals legislation COM(2025) 451 final, Omnibus VII Digital & data-regulation simplification package (AI, data, digital services), announced and pending publication.

2. [SLYCAN Trust \(2025a\)](#), "From Transition to Triage? Shifting Budget Priorities in the EU and Their Impact on the Green and Just Transition 2025 and Beyond," SLYCAN Trust EU Work Programme Knowledge Hub

This paper examines recent policy developments within the EU to assess whether its legal and financial instruments – and, by extension, its political direction – continue to align with the Green Deal’s core objectives, including reducing emissions by at least 55% by 2030 and achieving climate neutrality by 2050 under the European Climate Law.

We will explore this question in more detail by: 1. Summarising the changes brought by the omnibus proposals; 2. Analysing political reactions to those proposals; 3. Assessing possible links with budget proposals currently under discussion, 4. Examining changes to transparency and accountability rules; 5. Evaluating potential implications for the Green Deal; and 6. Concluding with a provisional assessment of likely trajectories.

II. The substantive omnibus packages in a nutshell

IN EU POLICYMAKING, AN OMNIBUS PROPOSAL REFERS TO A SINGLE LEGISLATIVE PACKAGE THAT INTRODUCES AMENDMENTS TO MULTIPLE LEGAL ACTS SIMULTANEOUSLY.

Rather than revising each regulation or directive separately, the European Commission bundles related changes into one comprehensive text in order to ensure consistency, streamline implementation, and accelerate the legislative process. omnibus packages are typically used to address cross-cutting issues, simplify administrative requirements, or respond to urgent political and economic developments.

Some of the recent omnibus proposals are especially consequential for the Green Deal because they alter the regulatory and budgetary conditions on which the Green Deal’s delivery depends. **Although omnibus packages do not formally repeal climate/environmental legislation, they can substantially reshape how that legislation functions in practice.**

By bundling amendments, fast-tracking multiple procedures, and reducing reporting and compliance obligations across different policy domains at once, they lower the regulatory baseline, weaken transparency and accountability mechanisms, and increase Member State discretion in implementation and enforcement. **As a result, omnibus reforms – together with other parallel revision proposals such as the EU Deforestation Regulation – dilute the operational force of the Green Deal while leaving its targets intact, creating a gap between the stated political ambition and the tools available to achieve it.**

The following section highlights the omnibus changes most relevant to the Green Deal and analyse the Council and Parliament’s reactions to these proposals. Their respective positions provide useful indications of their political priorities and broader direction, which may or may not align with the tendencies identified in budgetary documents such as the MFF, and whether sustainability and environmental EU goals are being adequately protected.

Figure 1. Timeline of the 2025 EU Omnibus Packages.
 Source: European Commission, “Simplification initiatives in the 2025 Work Programme”.

i. First Omnibus Package: Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) and the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD)

The Commission’s 2025 first simplification package, often referred to as the **sustainability omnibus**, aims to streamline three core Green Deal files: **the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD), the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD), and the EU Taxonomy framework**. It sharply narrows the scope of reporting (e.g., applying CSRD only to very large companies), delays and weakens due diligence obligations, and reduces the scope of EU’s Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) compliance obligations.

The rationale behind this amendment stems from the number of technical challenges that have emerged during the implementation of these frameworks, which has generated significant dissatisfaction across the industry.

Regarding the **CSRD**, its scope has been **narrowed** by raising both employee number and turnover thresholds, which results in the exclusion of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) from mandatory reporting requirements. **Those requirements are also significantly simplified by dropping certain sector-specific European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS), streamlining materiality assessments, and making some reporting elements voluntary.** These changes aim to reduce complexity and compliance burdens while claiming to maintain core transparency objectives aligned with the European Green Deal.

In regard to the **EU Taxonomy Regulation**, the Omnibus I **reduces the scope of reporting obligations**, aligning with the threshold established by the CSDDD scope. Furthermore, templates have been simplified and the **“Do No Significant Harm” (DNSH)** criteria streamlined. The assessment under DNSH is now limited to those with harmonized classifications and substances listed as being of very high concern. Moreover, **companies now can voluntarily report either on partial or full taxonomy alignment** and only assess activities that represent a significant percentage of their business volume.

For the **CSDDD**, changes follow the narrowing trend seen in CSRD, with **reduced coverage focused on the largest companies**. Obligations are now primarily centered on direct business partners, explicitly forbidding requests for information from smaller suppliers, thus severely **limiting downstream sustainability oversight within value chains**. Climate change transition plans, previously mandatory under CSDDD, have been removed or substantially relaxed. Similarly, **the duty to terminate business relationships in cases of severe or unmanageable adverse impacts has been softened to suspension and adoption of prevention/remediation plans**, easing compliance pressures and liability concerns. Additionally, the original EU-wide civil liability regime was dropped, delegating enforcement and access to justice mainly to MS, which risks inconsistent application across the Union³.

There is a separate process that follows the same line and logic as the proposals in the sustainability package. The revision of the **EU Deforestation Regulation** (Regulation (EU) 2023/1115) had created a conditionality for market access around accountability obligations with the objective that commodities/products should only be placed in the EU market or exported if they are deforestation-free, legal, and covered by a due diligence statement (DDS). This system was supposed to be supported by plot-level geolocation and a risk-based due diligence system.

The targeted ‘simplification’ revision package (Commission proposal COM(2025)652, alongside the Council’s later mandate) proposed to reduce administrative load by concentrating formal obligations upstream, creating a ‘downstream operator’ category with lighter duties, and introducing a simplified regime for micro/small primary operators in low-risk origins (including the possibility to use postal addresses instead of geolocation in certain cases).

3. HSF Kramer, "Omnibus Proposal Update," November 18, 2025.

This shifts transparency/accountability from a distributed chain of attestations toward a narrower set of upstream filings plus authority checks. Civil society leverage through complaints and review of competent authority action/inaction is largely maintained, but the documentary trail and the number of legally responsible nodes in the supply chain is reduced.

After a common position was reached by the Council on 19th November, the EP also endorsed the thrust of the proposed changes on 26th November.

Figure 2. Scope Reduction of CSRD and CSDDD under the Omnibus Proposal (Number of In-Scope Companies).

Sources: Accountancy Europe, Omnibus explained: key changes to CSRD proposed by the European Commission; Boston Consulting Group, The EU Omnibus Package; Regulatory & Compliance, CSRD Slashed: EU’s Corporate Sustainability Regulations Significantly Reduced.

* The figures presented are based on estimates from various independent analyses and have not yet been officially published by EU institutions. The actual numbers may vary as final decisions and official data are still pending.

Box 1. Council of the EU on the Omnibus Package I

On the sustainability omnibus, divisions have been revealed to be deep among MS. We can distinguish **two main political reactions** to the Commission’s sustainability omnibus: one taken by most northern and climate-progressive MS, and a second by parts of Central and Eastern Europe as well as MS with right-leaning political coalitions.

The first group – primarily Nordic countries such as Sweden, Finland, and Denmark, together with some Western MS including the Netherlands, Luxembourg, Germany, Ireland, and Austria–, has expressed **strong concerns about weakening core sustainability regulations** such as the CSRD, CSDDD, and CBAM. They generally support ambitious climate goals, greater corporate accountability, and stricter reporting standards. The latter political reaction is led by a group of MS including Poland, Hungary Czech Republic, Croatia, Slovenia, Italy, Malta, Cyprus, and – on specific dossiers– France as well as parts of Germany or Belgium. These countries generally argue for **measures aimed at reducing regulatory burdens and protecting industrial competitiveness**. They see the package as a necessary correction to over-regulation that could hinder economic growth.

The convergence of these opposing views resulted in a middle-ground compromise on the sustainability omnibus. The Council opinion narrows the scope of obligations, further dilutes some of the Commission’s most ambitious proposals, and extends certain deadlines. **While this compromise might make the package politically acceptable to a wider range of MS, it dilutes the regulatory impact and slows or even reverses progress towards the EU’s sustainability and climate goals.**

Box 2. European Parliament on the Omnibus Package I

The Omnibus has been broadly welcomed—especially by business and industry stakeholders—for its promise to improve usability and ease regulatory burdens. However, it has also been strongly condemned by the supporters of the Green Deal in the EP such as the S&D group and the Greens as well as by civil society for weakening the original intention and thereby creating uncertainty about the future of the EU's ambitious sustainability framework, to which many companies have dedicated significant resources, and its contribution to the fulfilment of EU Green Deal objectives. **Therefore, in the sustainability omnibus debate, the EP is split along lines similar to those seen during the [Climate Law revision](#). This indicates that political tensions around climate and sustainability policy extend far beyond a single legislative text.**

The EP's negotiating position seeks to narrow obligations even further, stressing the need to reduce regulatory burdens and preserve industrial competitiveness. Some of the most striking proposals include raising the CSRD threshold to 1,750 employees and limiting the CSDDD to companies with at least 5,000 employees and € 1.5 billion in turnover (see the Annex section).

To understand the practical implications of these changes, it is necessary to recall the original scope of the CSRD and CSDDD. Under the Commission's initial CSRD proposal, companies with 250+ employees (combined with turnover and balance sheet criteria) were expected to amount to roughly 50,000 undertakings across the EU. Raising the threshold to 1,750 employees would cut this scope by an estimated 70–80%, leaving only around 1–2% of companies originally captured.

For the CSDDD, the Commission's initial proposal covered approximately 13,000 companies. Under the European Parliament's revised thresholds, the scope has been drastically reduced, with only a small fraction of companies remaining in scope. This means the vast majority of EU economic operators would no longer be subject to the updated requirements, raising concerns that the core purpose of the sustainability framework is significantly weakened, if not rendered largely ineffective.

If we analyse the voting, we will find the centre-right (EPP), aligning with Renew and parts of ECR, played a key role in pushing through the Omnibus I position. They emphasise the need to reduce regulatory burdens, align with global deregulatory trends, and protect industrial competitiveness. As seen in the voting result, they tend to support narrowing CSRD scope and softening CSDDD and CBAM obligations, subject to some safeguards.

On the other hand, Greens/EFA, The Left, and a significant share of S&D criticise the package as a rollback of hard-won corporate accountability and transparency standards, warning that it undermines both the Green Deal and the EU's credibility on human rights and the environment.

ii. Second Omnibus Package: InvestEU Regulation, the European Fund for Strategic Investments (EFSI) and other funding instruments

This omnibus package aims to increase EU investment guarantees and simplify reporting requirements. It is designed to strengthen the EU's ability to mobilise private investment in key priority areas such as the green transition, digitalisation, and innovation. The Commission has publicly stated the package responds to slower economic growth as well as rising competitive pressure and geopolitical tensions.

It amends four EU regulations, with particular emphasis on the amendments to **Regulation (EU) 2021/523 (InvestEU Regulation)** and **Regulation (EU) 2015/1017 (EFSI Regulation)**. The **InvestEU Regulation** was implemented to boost public and private investment in key sectors such as innovation and sustainability, prioritizing under-invested areas. The **EFSI Regulation** established the European Fund for Strategic Investments, which guided the EU's investment strategy and stimulated private investment in transformative sectors, SMEs, and mid-cap companies.

Through its guarantee, EFSI was designed to mitigate investment risks and facilitate the financing of higher-risk projects, supporting economic recovery after the financial crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic.

Regarding the EFSI Regulation:

- The **scope of operations has expanded**; the EFSI guarantee can now support operations eligible under InvestEU and cover losses from combined arrangements.
- Reporting obligations have been simplified and combined, allowing for a **smoother re-use of legacy capacity**.
- Several administrative and procedural layers have been reduced, such as the removal of a subparagraph from Article 22(1).

Regarding the InvestEU Regulation:

- The proposal clearly **defines the dual purpose of the programme** as both an EU guarantee and an InvestEU financial instrument and sets a specific amount for the additional provisioning of the EU guarantee.
- It expands the definition of shared management funds, allowing their use to reinforce the InvestEU guarantee.
- It enables more flexible blending across different EU programmes and budgetary periods and permits the **reuse, "reflow," or "redeployment" of resources**.
- It eliminates the **"multiplier effect"** on investment guarantees; consequently, **performance guarantee operations are now exempted**.
- It simplifies **reporting obligations** for implementing partners and national compartments (aimed to reduce administrative burden, especially for SMEs/final recipients).

To analyse the effect of these reforms, **it is important to note that around 40% of current InvestEU operations contribute to climate action and sustainability goals.** Consequently, the agreement to strengthen the EU's investment capacity should further boost programmes related to the green transition, clean energy, sustainable infrastructure, and innovation. **Moreover, lowering and simplifying administrative burdens may broaden the base of potential investors willing to finance sustainable projects, but concerns about transparency and accountability exist also with regard to these changes.**

Therefore, following the narrative raised during the Omnibus I discussions, certain Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) warn that reducing reporting requirements and allowing more flexible blending may weaken environmental, social, and transparency safeguards.

WITHOUT STRONG MONITORING, SIMPLIFICATION MAY LEAD TO SIGNIFICANT "GREEN LABELLING" OF INVESTMENTS OR EVEN DOUBLE COUNTING.

In addition, some stakeholders have highlighted that while the reflow of resources can prevent inefficiencies, it also risks undermining the transparency and accountability of the system by making it harder to track allocations, approvals, and outcomes.

The removal of the "multiplier effect" and the expansion of eligible operations may also incentivise a shift towards lower-risk projects that do not genuinely require EU intervention. This would run contrary to the Commission's objective of increasing transformative investments and could hinder access to funding for riskier, innovative, or early-stage projects that depend on EU support.

Finally, while the package claims to reinforce the green transition, it has been argued that increased flexibility might make it easier to finance projects with unclear or limited climate benefits.⁴ **Although 40% of InvestEU operations currently should support climate and sustainability objectives, this share could be diluted by new competitiveness priorities if proper safeguards are not maintained and fully integrated.**

Box 3. Council of the EU on the Omnibus Package II

The Council's rationale stresses the importance of boosting EU competitiveness and opening new investment opportunities in key policy areas for the EU. Within those key areas, it emphasised the need for investments on the **"Competitiveness Compass"** and **"Clean Industrial Deal."** Under its mandate, the Council supports the increase of the EU guarantee and the combination of different legacy programmes. Another key priority is administrative simplification for implementing partners, financial intermediaries and final recipients. This is combined with the lowering of the reporting load by revising the SME definition, and reducing both the required indicators and the frequency of reporting. **We find within the Council a strong endorsement of the Omnibus II reforms for InvestEU which closely mirrors the Commission's rationale and proposal.**

4. Alice Bertram (2025), "Deregulating to No Avail: How the Omnibus Package Falls Short in Simplifying Key EU Green Deal Instruments," *Intereconomics*, Vol. 60, No. 3.

Box 4. European Parliament on the Omnibus Package II

In June 2025, the EP's Committees on Budgets (BUDG) and Economic and Monetary Affairs (ECON) adopted this package on InvestEU programme simplification. **In contrast with the previously mentioned Omnibus I package, this package was adopted a few months after the Commission's proposal by a clear majority, reflecting a relatively broad political consensus.** It emphasised that the reforms should encourage a more effective functioning of the system, especially for SMEs, through the lowering of administrative burden. Conveying the EP's position, **the rapporteur expresses that the EU needs "scale, simplicity, and ambition" rather than a patchwork of overlapping instruments.** Among these objectives are the mobilisation of public and private funds and the support of the green and digital transitions, as well as innovation.

Aligning with the Council's mandate, the EP demands a significant increase in the EU guarantees. The convergence was confirmed by the reaching of a provisional inter-institutional agreement by September 2025. **While the EP's ambition seems to be somewhat higher when it comes to guarantees and advisory support, the proposed measures are broadly aligned. The Council frames the reforms in terms of competitiveness and mobilising investments in times of geopolitical uncertainty. However, the EP seems to situate the investments as a central point for the green and digital transition.**

iii. Third Omnibus Package: Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)

The Common Agricultural Policy, or CAP, remains the crucial instrument of the EU's agricultural policy, aiming to support farmers, promote sustainable farming, and ensure food security. During the last thirty years, particularly under the Green Deal and the Farm to Fork strategy, the EU had gradually improved CAP's alignment with broader environmental and climate goals, mainly through the **Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAEC)** compliance requirements for receiving basic direct payments (Pillar I) and the **voluntary agri-environment-climate (AEC)** measures under Pillar II.

The CAP's greening led to strong farmer protests in several MS with large agricultural sectors, such as France, Germany, and Poland. Consequently, the third omnibus package was presented on 14 May 2025 as a **political response** to these protests, announced as an attempt to balance environmental ambitions with practical flexibility for farmers. **The Commission's emphasis on modernizing agriculture, making it greener, and reducing environmental harm had been criticised as too restrictive or costly due to the strong influence of agricultural and food industry interests, which are powerful drivers in many MS.** Some of the most important proposals in the omnibus are:

- **Greater flexibility and leeway on conditionalities tied to accessing agricultural subsidies**. Notably, an exemption for smaller farms from certain controls and penalties, considerably reducing their administrative burden.
- **Expanded (or revised) definitions for environmental conditions** covering permanent grassland, peatland, and wetland protection as well as watercourse management. The package revises GAEC 2, 6, and 7 to increase flexibility and reduce certain obligations, which is intended to lower compliance costs but may weaken environmental safeguards.
- Introduction of **complementary crisis payments** for farmers affected by floods, droughts, or other climate-driven disasters.
- **Higher flat-rate aid ceilings:**
 - Up to €2,500 for small farmers;
 - Up to €50,000 for small farm development initiatives.
- Streamlined strategic plan amendments through which only significant changes would require Commission approval. This attempts to speed up most administrative procedures, enhancing flexibility for MS.
- **Reduced inspection frequency**, benefiting smaller farms and reducing their bureaucratic burden.
- Broad **exemption of organic farmers** from cross-compliance obligations.

While the Green Deal pushes for more sustainable agriculture, the CAP reforms appear to bend to political pressures and the requests for a pragmatic approach to implementation. Some experts have warned that relaxing conditionalities may slow down environmental progress, while others argue that these changes are necessary to maintain farmer buy-in and food security in a sector especially vulnerable to climate change-related disruptions.

HOWEVER, IT IS UNDENIABLE THAT THE CAP REFORM CARRIES SIGNIFICANT CONSEQUENCES FOR ENVIRONMENTAL AMBITION AND POLICY COHERENCE.

The weakening of environmental standards and the relaxing of GAEC 2, 6, and 7 requirements reduce pressure on farms to protect biodiversity and conserve natural resources, among others. Furthermore, the CAP is the EU's largest single budget line/category, adding up to almost 30% of total EU spending. **A decrease in green conditionalities will hinder MS's capacity to meet 2030 climate targets and shift pressure to other sectors to compensate.** However, those sectors – such as industry or energy – are subject to similar political pressures.

Box 5. Council of the EU on the Omnibus Package III

In agriculture, a broad majority in the Council has called for simplification and relaxation of environmental rules within the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). This strong push stems largely from **intense pressure by powerful farm lobbies and widespread rural protests**—often supported and even engineered by far-right groups⁵—across several countries, particularly in France, Poland, Germany, and the Netherlands. Even governments with strong environmental credentials have been reluctant to block CAP simplification measures, largely because agriculture is a politically sensitive sector in many MS and farmers represent a significant and vocal constituency. **Politicians and the government fear that opposing the rule relaxation could lead to domestic backlash, protests, or even electoral losses.** Thus, despite their green credentials, some northern and western European governments, such as the Netherlands, Germany, and France, have prioritised political pragmatism and the avoidance of unrest over strict environmental ambition in this context.

Box 6. European Parliament on the Omnibus Package III

On CAP simplification, EP discussions have been less polarized. While some groups and individual MEPs voiced concerns about lowering GAEC standards and weakening environmental conditionality, the EP overall endorsed the agriculture Omnibus as a necessary response to farmers’ protests and administrative overload. At a moment of intense political pressure, the drive to show responsiveness to rural voters has outweighed the defence of environmental ambition. **Crucially, the EP framed the reform as an emergency correction rather than a structural change of the Green Deal.** This helped consolidate a broader majority in favour of the simplification measures, especially those exempting smaller farms from certain controls, reducing penalties, and easing requirements linked to GAEC rules for the CAP payments. The modified rules were some of the most visible “green” obligations for farmers and also seen as creating excessive administrative and operational constraints.

This episode also highlights a recurring pattern in EU policymaking: when environmental commitments collide with immediate socio-economic pressures, particularly from politically sensitive sectors such as agriculture, the EP tends to give priority to short-term relief. Overall, the EP is more defensive on procedural and transparency issues in the sustainability Omnibus (insisting on scrutiny, complaining about rushed consultations and thin impact assessments) but less willing to oppose deregulation or simplification when it is framed as competitiveness or relief for struggling sectors.

5. Farmers' protests exploited to spread fake news about EU climate policy, study nails European far-right, EU News, 3 June 2024.

iv. Fourth Omnibus Package: Regulatory Simplification, SMEs, and Digital Compliance

The Fourth Omnibus is a major simplification package part of a broader strategy of the commission to cut red tape and streamline regulations for businesses, especially for SMEs and small mid-cap enterprises. Its goal is to reduce administrative burdens by at least 25% for all companies and 35% for SMEs by the end of the current mandate.

The Omnibus responds to a large complaint of small businesses regarding the disproportionate burden imposed to them and the complexity of regulations. A lower bureaucratic hurdle is intended to favor growth, innovation and job creation as SMEs represent around 99% of all businesses in the EU. The following bullet point summarize the main changes introduced by the package, each modifying a different legislative act:

- It simplifies **requirements on the protection of animals** for small-scale establishment crying out procedures for scientific purposes reducing reporting frequency and inspections.
- It streamlines and clarifies obligations regarding the **presence of hazardous substances in electrical and electronic equipment**.
- It simplifies the **authorisation and renewal process for biocidal products**, particularly for SMEs.
- It simplifies **tender procedures** for SMEs, such as allowing for lower thresholds and streamlined qualification criteria.
- It reduces disclosure and reporting requirements for micro-entities and SMEs on **financial statements, audit obligations and related reports**.
- It simplifies **waste management plans and reports** for small producers of waste.
- It eases requirements and documentation for small-scale producers on record-keeping and reporting on the **protection of animals at the time of killing**.
- It simplifies compliance and reporting procedures under the **European Emissions Trading System** for small emitters falling below certain thresholds.
- It introduces simplified requirements for SMEs regarding **energy audits and reporting**.

Furthermore, throughout the various modifications, **the package promotes the use of digital tools to simplify procedures, improve access to information and interoperability, and facilitate the processing of requests**. It may be argued that clarification, digitalisation, and streamlining reporting may fasten and help businesses better comply with environmental regulations. However, **by cutting down reporting requirements, there is a risk that crucial data may be lost or underreported**.

Moreover, less frequent or simplified reporting could lead to the creation of information gaps, hindering the assessment of whether companies are actually meeting environmental standards. Additionally, fewer checks or inspections might also encourage businesses to deprioritize sustainable practices. Finally, it must be considered that not all SMEs have equal access to digital skills and the necessary infrastructure, which could reduce effective compliance and hamper the just transition.

v. Fifth Omnibus Package: Defence Readiness Framework

The Commission's Defence Readiness Omnibus, adopted 17 June 2025 and transmitted to the EP and Council, is a package of simplification measures meant to remove legal/administrative bottlenecks for the ramp-up of Europe's defence industrial capacity. It consists (in legislative terms) of two proposed regulations and one proposed directive, plus draft delegated acts. **The main points of relevance in the context of this brief is that it eases the impact of certain environmental legislation with regard to defence and security operations.** It proposes targeted changes to REACH, CLP, Biocidal Products, and Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) rules "as regards defence readiness"⁶. Notably, **it would allow MS, where necessary in the interests of defence, to grant exemptions from some of these regimes** (and also allows security-related exemptions from certain POPs reporting to protect sensitive information).

While the proposal stresses it "does not lower standards" in principle, it does include procedural accelerators (tight deadlines and tacit approval) that may, in practice, reduce the time available for environmental scrutiny. More explicitly, the separate regulation on chemicals / environment-related legislation allows MS, under certain conditions, to exempt defence-related substances/products from parts of REACH / CLP / biocides / POPs requirements "in the interests of defence". Capturing the new approach of the European Commission it is worth noting that the permitting regulation proposal acknowledges that, due to urgency, no impact assessment was delivered before adoption, with a staff working document promised afterwards, but not yet delivered.

vi. Sixth Omnibus Package: Chemical Regulatory Framework

The simplification omnibus proposal on chemicals is part of a broader package encompassed within the European Chemicals Industry Action Plan, which aims to support the competitiveness and clean transition of the EU chemical sector.

The chemicals industry is the **fourth largest manufacturing sector in the EU**, and this plan responds to recent challenges such as high energy costs, increasing unfair global competition (mostly due to lower environmental and safety standards in non-EU countries) and weak demand. Some of the major changes introduced include:

- 'Stop-the-clock' postponement of many "classification, labelling, and packaging" (CLP) provisions.
- Simplification of CLP labelling and advertising rules to make a more workable framework in practice.
- Simplifications for the Fertilising Products Regulation, easing the requirements and reducing compliance costs.
- Several delegated acts to standardise formats and procedures.
- Measures aimed at protecting critical supply chains.
- Strengthening of the European Chemical Agency mandate.

6. For more information, see European Parliament, Omnibus II – Optimising the Use of Several EU Instruments to Boost Investment (Legislative Train, carriage 'Second Omnibus Package on Investment Simplification').

Some of these measures have a direct impact on public health and environmental protection. The delayed implementation of CLP provisions slows the identification and communication of chemical hazards, which undermines consumer protection, workplace safety, and environmental safeguards. Furthermore, certain stakeholders have suggested that this may also postpone the uptake of safer alternatives.

Easing requirements under the Fertilising Products Regulation can lower costs for producers, but it will also weaken controls on polluting substances and reduce their traceability.

These risks are amplified by the standardisation and simplification of procedures. **Faster processing and reduced depth of assessment increase the likelihood that hazardous chemicals remain on the market longer or are insufficiently regulated.**

INDUSTRY PRESSURE AND CHALLENGES ARE DOMINATING THE POLITICAL DISCOURSE, WHICH COULD, IN THE LONG TERM, DILUTE GREEN AMBITIONS IN A KEY SECTOR FOR ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY.

Lastly, the Action Plan driving Omnibus VI appears focused on protecting supply chains and enhancing the global competitiveness of the EU chemical industry.

Box 7. Council of the EU on the Omnibus Package VI

The Council has approached this Omnibus package with a clearer prioritisation of economic feasibility, legal certainty and manageable transition for industry, especially SMEs. Its “stop-the-clock” decision leading to the postponement of many 2024-revised CLP requirements until 1 January 2028, exemplifies that **the Council attempts to give businesses the “necessary legal certainty”, avoiding the “unnecessary burden” of overlapping regulatory changes.**

Beyond timing, the Council’s negotiating mandate for the rest of the Omnibus simplifies formatting, labelling, packaging, and advertisement and distance-sales requirements across chemicals, cosmetics, and fertilising products. For cosmetics, for instance, the Council reintroduced the requirement for nanomaterial notification and maintained stricter oversight of CMR (carcinogenic, mutagenic, or reprotoxic) substances than in the Commission’s initial draft. This may indicate that while it openly supports simplification, it also seeks to safeguard core issues related to health and protection of the environment. On the other hand, **the reintroduction of certain safety-sensitive requirements may suggest some internal balancing, likely reflecting diverging Member State interests** and not a common and general attempt to further safeguard the population.

On the “One Substance, One Assessment” (OSOA) package, the Council pushed for more transparent and clear responsibilities, better inter-agency cooperation, and efficient data-sharing to avoid duplication. It emphasised the need for OSOA to ensure that scientific and regulatory tasks are streamlined without sacrificing quality. Its contribution is therefore focused on the attainment of a workable model: simplifying where possible, and protecting where needed.

Box 8. European Parliament on the Omnibus Package VI

The EP's position in chemicals regulation has stressed that simplification and streamlining must not come at the expense of public health and environmental protection. During its negotiations on the OSOA package, the EP secured a broader scope for the common data platform than initially proposed, including not only mandatory data but also voluntarily submitted scientific studies or data on medical substances. Furthermore, it has included a requirement of publicly releasable data being made accessible under EU transparency rules.

Moreover, the EP insisted on mechanisms for regular human-monitoring data and a database of safer alternatives to dangerous chemicals. With these measures they attempted to ensure that risk assessments are grounded in up-to-date science and that substitution towards safer substances is facilitated. **In doing so, the EP's contribution has been to raise the ambition of the legislation, turning it into not merely a simplification instrument but also a more coherent and science-based regulation capable of better detecting emerging risks, supporting safer alternatives, and ensuring public access.** Overall, it seeks to build a more coherent framework rather than simply pursuing deregulation.

When it came to the CLP-related postponement ("stop-the-clock"), the EP voted in favor—aligning with the Council—but its broader legislative work shows that the EP's interest is not just in delaying or easing regulatory burdens, but it also aims at strengthening data governance, transparency, and precautionary capacity during that period.

vii Seventh Omnibus Package: Digital Legislation

The Commission's Digital Omnibus, presented on 19 November 2025 and now in the hands of the European Parliament and the Council, is a package of targeted simplification measures, **it is built around two proposed regulations: (i) a Digital Omnibus Regulation** proposal introducing technical amendments across a broad set of existing digital legislation **and (ii) a Digital Omnibus on AI Regulation proposal** with targeted changes to facilitate the "timely, smooth and proportionate" implementation of parts of the AI Act.

The Digital Omnibus is not an "environment" file, but its adoption in the current form could have negative knock-on effects for climate and environmental action, mainly by weakening the open-data transparency infrastructure that underpins monitoring, accountability, and evidence-based policy. In particular, the proposal repeals the Open Data Directive and folds its rules (and parts of the Data Governance Act) into the Data Act, and introduces new possibilities for public bodies to charge higher fees and impose special conditions on re-use by "very large enterprises" (notably gatekeepers).

Because the EU's "high-value datasets" explicitly include earth observation as well as environment and meteorological data—core inputs for climate risk analysis, pollution tracking, and independent scrutiny—any move from default "open and frictionless re-use" toward more conditional / priced access for some key re-users risks raising barriers, fragmenting access across MS, and making it harder for watchdogs, researchers, and service providers to reproduce analyses at scale. **Even if the intent is fairness/competition, from a transparency and accountability lens, the concern is that the omnibus creates more discretion and complexity around public environmental data re-use precisely when the EU is increasingly "mainstreaming" green objectives into broader competitiveness and security agendas.**

III. How these omnibus packages relate to the budgetary proposals

While the substantive omnibus packages and the budget proposals (MFF revision; 2028–2034 MFF; Ukraine Facility and competitiveness instruments) are formally and procedurally separate, they are substantively aligned.

They entail a lowering of expectations in the case of the Omnibus packages and a reduction in available resources on the budgetary side. **Together, they clearly reflect dimensions of a coordinated political shift: budgetary reprioritisation and regulatory rollback:**

On the budget side, the new MFF proposal and mid-term revision move resources towards defence, security, competitiveness, and flexibility, while dispersing and diluting dedicated environmental and just transition envelopes. For instance, **previous reports have described the MFF proposal as reducing dedicated Green Deal funding and dispersing it across various budgetary headings, while introducing only limited mechanisms for accountability and transparency⁷.**

On the regulatory side, omnibus packages such as the ones described in the sections above—e.g., on sustainability, investments, agricultural policy, defence, chemical regulation, and digital legislation—**follow a similar logic: reducing or postponing non-budgetary obligations that were meant to underpin the Green Deal.** Some of the main examples are softer environmental conditionalities for CAP payments with relaxed GAEC standards, lighter corporate sustainability reporting and due diligence, more flexible reflow of funding resources, and the weakening of controls on polluting substances.

Taken together, these developments suggest a strategic rebalancing within the EU. Competitiveness, cost relief, and short-term sectoral stabilisation have risen to become overarching criteria not only financially and monetarily but also for regulatory standards.

THE GREEN DEAL AND ITS LONG-TERM GOALS ARE INCREASINGLY EXPECTED TO FIT WITHIN A COMPETITIVENESS AND SECURITY-FIRST PARADIGM RATHER THAN BE THE STRUCTURING AND GUIDING FRAMEWORK.

This shift echoes concerns raised by analysts about the EU's changing focus in the face of geopolitical tensions, economic pressures, social demands, etc.

7. See footnote n. 2.

While the new MFF proposal formally retains the potential to embed sustainability objectives across sectors through cross-policy alignment, this potential is increasingly undermined by parallel regulatory developments.

IN PRACTICE, HOPES FOR AN INTEGRATED APPROACH TO COMPETITIVENESS AND SECURITY THAT INCORPORATES CLIMATE-RELATED CONCERNS APPEAR TO FADE WHEN EXAMINING RECENT EU REGULATORY REFORMS.

Key instruments such as the CAP, the CSRD, and the CSDDD were designed to provide a regulatory backbone for the green transition in agriculture and industry. The CAP sought to incentivise farmers to adopt more environmentally sustainable practices while compensating for compliance costs, whereas the CSRD and the CSDDD established transparency and due-diligence obligations aimed at strengthening environmental and social responsibility across corporate activity. **The weakening or postponement of these frameworks therefore limits the capacity of budgetary instruments alone to deliver a coherent green transition.**

All things considered, the reforms to both the investment framework (InvestEU/EFSI) and the EU's chemical regulatory regime reinforce the impression of a broader strategic rebalancing. In both areas, **Omnibus-driven changes tilt the policy mix toward competitiveness, industrial resilience, and short-term cost relief, even when this comes at the expense of environmental ambition or regulatory stringency.**

On the investment side, simplification, flexible blending, or the removal of the multiplier effect hinder the tracking of green projects and lower the transformative potential. On the chemicals side, postponements of CLP obligations, simplified labelling rules, and eased compliance requirements reflect a prioritisation of industrial workability.

When considered together, these developments suggest that the EU's green transition is increasingly expected to adjust to a competitiveness- and security-first paradigm rather than shape it. This shift mirrors concerns raised by analysts about the EU's changing priorities under geopolitical and economic pressures, and appears to indicate a further dilution of the Green Deal within the EU policy agenda.

IV. Transparency and accountability: substantive and procedural risks

Aside from their effectiveness in reducing complexity and appealing to industrial and agricultural sectors, **the omnibus legislative packages collectively introduce significant challenges to transparency and accountability mainly on two levels.**

These two levels are its **substantive opacity** and **procedural shortcuts**, both risking undermining the effective implementation of priorities like the Green Deal and even the EU governance's legitimacy.

I. Substantive Opacity

The Omnibus packages, by nature, bundle together many changes into single comprehensive horizontal acts. This consolidation or bundling often leads to a lack of clarity about the real impact of the changes, hindering the possibility of stakeholders and citizens of getting a clear indication of its effects on the Green Deal. For instance, a combination of narrower CSRD scope, weaker or softer due diligence requirements, and looser GAEC standards in the CAP together with the simplification proposed in the chemicals package moves the baseline against which "green" budgetary spending should be judged. **This shift is rarely made explicit in budget debates but will affect overall ambition.** Furthermore, in the investment domain, looser reporting requirements, the removal of the multiplier effect and the encouragement of flexible investment blending leads to a focus on faster capital deployment, making it harder to trace projects with a real climate value. Following the same political shift, the postponement of CLP provisions, simplified labelling rules, and eased compliance obligations similarly prioritise industrial predictability and competitiveness over precaution and environmental protection.

The cumulative effect is a weakening of green standards without an explicit political decision to do so. While broader budget discussions or political debates have not made it explicit, these substantive changes effectively shift the environmental ambitions of EU policy. **As it is hard to discern whether it is advancing or retreating on its climate and sustainability goals, or where those changes can be found, opposition or public awareness remains limited.** This lack of transparency obscures accountability, it hampers informed public scrutiny and debate over how EU funds and regulatory frameworks contribute to or detract from the Green Deal's objectives.

II. Procedural Shortcuts

Several omnibus initiatives have been criticised for accelerated timetables, limited consultations, and absent or minimal impact assessments. This mirrors the concerns already raised around fast-tracked CAP amendments in 2024 and has prompted warnings from the European Ombudsman⁸ and legal scholars about “omnibus lawmaking” eroding the safeguards of ordinary EU legislative procedure.

This procedural opacity means that decisions with far-reaching consequences for environmental policy and EU governance are made without full transparency or adequate participation from all stakeholders, including affected communities. **Fast-tracked procedures—motivated in response to civil unrest by the agricultural sector or certain industrial and corporate stakeholders—may lead to the disregard of unintended consequences or other possible alternative approaches.**

When this substantive and procedural opacity—gradually reshaping the regulatory landscape—is combined with the budgetary practices highlighted in our [previous brief](#)⁹, such as ex-ante climate coefficients, special instruments operating over the ceilings, and wide scope for relabelling spending as green, the result is a double challenge to accountability. **On one hand, the regulatory framework itself becomes harder to track, with complex, bundled amendments diluting the clarity of obligations and ambitions. And, on the other hand, not only do the rules become harder to follow, but so does the financial reality, making the Green Deal’s real trajectory increasingly dependent on expert reconstructions of behind-the-scenes political processes rather than transparent and openly debated political choices.** This combination threatens democratic oversight and risks eroding public trust in the EU’s ability to deliver on its climate commitments. Moreover, it raises the barrier for citizens, civil society, and even institutional actors themselves to hold decision-makers accountable or to understand how public money and regulatory powers are shaping—or failing to shape—Europe’s green transition. In practice, this quiet accumulation of opacity and flexibility amounts to a subtle lowering of ambition: a recalibration of the Green Deal from a structuring principle of EU governance to a secondary consideration within a competitiveness- and crisis-driven policy paradigm.

8. See European Ombudsman, “European Ombudsman Opens Strategic Inquiry into the European Commission’s Use of Omnibus Legislation,”

9. See footnote n. 2.

V. Conclusion

Despite collectively weakening its operational power, the substantive omnibus packages do not, on their own and as of yet, signal an overall repeal of the Green Deal. As in the case of the MFF proposal, targets remain formally in place, and many sectoral policies continue to move, albeit unevenly, in a green direction. A clear illustration of the previous dynamic can be seen in the European Parliament's votes on 13 November 2025. On the same day, the EP adopted both its position on the amendment to the European Climate Law—establishing the EU's 2040 emission reduction target—and its negotiating position on the regulatory simplification of the CSRD and CSDDD under the sustainability omnibus. Although the two texts point in opposite directions in terms of ambition, both were approved by similar majorities, revealing a **political readiness to endorse long-term climate targets while simultaneously weakening the impact of regulatory tools needed to deliver them.**

Fragmented political will within EU institutions, combined with competing MS interests, exacerbate regulatory dilution and hinder the coherent delivery of Green Deal objectives. The most recent addition to the omnibus packages - the eighth proposal, the so-called "environment package"—confirms this overall trend by bundling targeted amendments across three main areas, notably industrial emissions and circular economy, geospatial/environmental data, and environmental assessments and permitting. **These amendments point in the same direction as the other packages and, under the banner of simplification and easing of the bureaucratic burden, weaken safeguards for nature, health, and transparency at a moment when enforcement gaps are already large.**

Thus, despite the reassertion of climate commitments, these packages materially lower and blur the regulatory baseline against which the EU's environmental commitments are measured. At the same time, budget proposals shift spending towards security and competitiveness, failing to ring-fence funds essential for a transformative green and just transition.

The positions of the Council and the European Parliament taken together reveal a shared willingness to retain the Green Deal's long-term targets while simultaneously accepting or even pushing for substantial short-term regulatory weakening. The Council's mandate has broadly aligned with the Commission's proposals, generally prioritising feasibility, competitiveness, and stability across sectors, from corporate sustainability rules to CAP conditionalities and chemicals regulation. Its compromises move consistently in the direction of lowering and delaying obligations, probably due to strong domestic pressures from industry, agriculture, and security interests. The European Parliament, by contrast, seems to be increasingly fragmented. While it continues to endorse ambitious climate objectives as the 2040 targets, it has also supported many of the same simplification measures, particularly when framed as competitiveness-enhancing or as responses to civil unrest.

This duality has produced outcomes where the EP defends procedural transparency more strongly than the Council yet still supports substantive weakening of tools such as CSRD, CSDDD, or GAEC standards, and elements of chemicals and digital regulation. **Overall, both institutions lean toward a scenario in which climate ambition remains rhetorically intact but it is progressively decoupled from the regulatory and budgetary instruments that are needed to deliver it.**

In the scenario framework of the past policy brief "From Transition to Triage? Shifting Budget Priorities in the EU and Their Impact on the Green and Just Transition 2025 and Beyond," this combination of deregulatory omnibus proposals and reoriented budgets reinforces a Fragmented Scenario in which climate/environment and social goals persist as cross-cutting labels or political rhetoric, but without the regulatory bite, clear spending envelopes, or robust monitoring needed to guarantee delivery. **The omnibus tools are presented as an intelligent simplification and crisis adaptation tool, yet in the absence of countervailing transparency and accountability mechanisms, they contribute to a quiet downgrading of the Green Deal from a strategic lodestar to a negotiable parameter within a competitiveness-driven agenda.**

Furthermore, the lack of protection frameworks to ensure sustainability and environmental protection risks future policy incoherence. While substantive opacity may delay public response and mask conflicting priorities, economic competitiveness and environmental sustainability are clearly managed through compromises rather than integrated strategies. Long-term, climate-related policy degradation or the failure to achieve stated objectives may lead to an erosion of public trust.

IN PARALLEL, THE USE OF PROCEDURAL SHORTCUTS RISKS DEBILITATION OF DEMOCRATIC LEGITIMACY IN EUROPEAN INSTITUTIONS.

The forthcoming **Circular Economy Act**, currently at the consultation stage, **represents another critical opportunity that will either reinforce or further undermine the Green Deal's operational strength.** Currently framed as a competitiveness and resilience tool rather than as a Green Deal ambition-raiser, it remains to be seen whether it will add to the deregulatory omnibus moves. **This will depend on whether it prioritizes robust accountability and clear EU-wide standards or falls into the pattern of deregulatory simplification.**

Unless meaningful countervailing measures are introduced, the continuation of current trends—where accelerated omnibus lawmaking is paired with a dilution of green budget priorities—risks reducing the Green Deal from a functioning policy architecture to a largely rhetorical commitment. Preventing this outcome will require EU institutions to restore transparency and accountability, ring-fence green spending, and ensure that simplification measures do not hollow out key environmental safeguards. **Without such rectifying steps, the patterns across the Council and Parliament will reinforce a fragmented trajectory for the Green Deal: neither dismantled nor meaningfully protected, but gradually diluted through political compromise, accelerated decision-making, and an emerging focus on competitiveness and security over ecological governance.**

VI. Annex

Policy Area	European Commission's Proposal	Council of the EU's Position	European Parliament's Position
Scope	≥1000 employees and €450m EU turnover required for in-scope non-EU & EU large companies	Same as Commission; allows exemptions for some holding companies	Some higher thresholds, broader exemptions for subsidiaries and group-level reporting
SMEs	Removes listed SMEs from mandatory scope	SME exemption harmonised; lighter regime, clearer opt-outs	Stronger opt-outs for both SMEs and group subsidiaries, longer transition periods
Value Chain Obligations	Due diligence on tier 1 (direct) suppliers only, not entire value chain	Same as Commission, plus legal protection for small partners to refuse complex data requests from large clients	Further limits on data requests to SMEs, greater rights of refusal, and wider exemptions for indirect partners
Reporting (ESRS)	Reduces mandatory datapoints, aims for global/International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) interoperability, revising ESRS (2.0)	Endorses streamlining but wants sector guidance to be non-binding	Favors even further simplification and avoiding duplicative reporting, quantitative focus
Assurance	Limited assurance required from outset; reasonable assurance standard to be defined by 2028	Accepts limited assurance; reserves possibility to delay for some cases, targeted guidelines on scope	Emphasizes protection of trade secrets and IP when providing assurance; also favors limited assurance
EU Taxonomy	Introduces optional/ voluntary Taxonomy key performance indicators (KPIs), new materiality and green asset thresholds	Broadly supports, but seeks more flexible application and new reporting KPIs	Wants to end optional reporting and introduce more obligations to avoid "greenwashing," refines thresholds
Civil Liability & Penalties	Dropped original single-EU civil liability regime; retains national frameworks but requires access-to-justice guarantees. Initially proposed a 5% turnover penalty cap	Removes cap, allows national discretion for penalties, provides guidance only	Partially reinstates penalties cap, but with more proportionality clauses and judicial oversight
Digital / Technological Tools	Mandates development of a centralized EU digital reporting portal for templates, data sharing, and compliance support	Endorses portal; suggests linking to tendering/funding opportunities as an incentive	Backs portal with additional resources, proposes making it a legal compliance interface for all sustainability disclosures
Gold-Plating	Restricts MS from adding stricter ("gold-plated") obligations on most core articles; technical scope for risk exceptions	Permits some gold-plating for emerging sectoral or market risks, subject to review	More cautious, prefers minimal national divergence except for very defined cases

Table 1. Institutional positions of the Commission, Council and Parliament based on their proposal/mandates on the CSRD and CSDD.

Based on: HSF Kramer. (November 18, 2025). Omnibus Proposal Update Where To Next? Riding the Omnibus.

Related publications from the EU work programme:

BUDGETARY TRENDS IN THE EUROPEAN UNION AND ITS MEMBER STATES AND IMPLICATIONS FOR CLIMATE FINANCE

POLICY BRIEF

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY This brief examines the budgetary trends of the European Union (EU) and its 27 Member States from 2020 to 2025, and projects how trends through 2024 may affect international climate finance. Following the COVID-19 pandemic, the war in Ukraine, rising inflation, and global geopolitical tensions, EU and national budgets of Member States have increasingly shifted toward defence, energy security, and industrial competitiveness. As a result, climate finance risks being deprioritized, affecting the EU's ability to fulfil its obligations under the UNFCCC and Paris Agreement and support the scaling up of climate finance in line with the new collective quantified goal established at COP29.

At the EU level, the proposed new Multiannual Financial Framework sets record-high spending levels, yet a substantial portion is allocated to defence, strategic autonomy, and crisis-response initiatives rather than climate and development aid. The budget structure has been redesigned to be more flexible but also less transparent: previously ring-fenced climate or development funds have been merged into broader envelopes, making it increasingly difficult to track actual allocations to climate objectives. At the national level, Member State budgets mirror these tendencies, with major donors cutting climate and development finance while sharply increasing defence expenditure. Political priorities reflect this shift, as most governing parties across Europe now emphasize economic and security concerns over climate action.

The implications for international climate finance are significant, as bilateral climate-related finance is sharply declining. Although multilateral finance through Multilateral Development Banks is rising or being maintained, it fails to compensate for reductions in public finance. This is largely because it relies predominantly on non-grant instruments and disproportionately favors economically attractive sectors and regions. A clear paradox emerges: European Multilateral Development Banks, such as the European Investment Bank, are expanding their overall investment portfolios, yet most of the gains are retained within Europe, resulting in stagnation rather than growth in global climate-related support.

A product of SLYCAN Trust October 2025

FROM TRANSITION TO TRIAGE?

SHIFTING BUDGET PRIORITIES IN THE EU AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE GREEN AND JUST TRANSITION 2025 AND BEYOND

POLICY BRIEF

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY The European Green Deal was launched as a cornerstone of the EU's commitment to achieving climate neutrality, alongside the digital and industrial transformation. While its implementation has led to significant progress, its goal of embedding long-term sustainability at the heart of economic policy remains only partially fulfilled, with signs of growing divergence. Recent years have seen a notable shift in fiscal and political priorities driven by geopolitical conflicts such as the Russo-Ukrainian war, the COVID-19 pandemic, and growing economic tensions, including the US-China trade war. In response, the EU and its member states have prioritized strengthening Europe's resilience to stress, aiming at building an independent, prosperous, secure, and thriving society and economy—as reflected in the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) proposal for 2028–2034.

Although the EU continues to uphold its global climate commitments publicly, the MFF proposal raises concerns by appearing to dilute these promises, with questions about the robustness of monitoring mechanisms and the scope and objectives of future green investments. The outlook at the level of EU Member States appears even more concerning, as climate-related development aid is decreasing, climate policies are weakening, and political instability limits the approach to long-term challenges such as climate change and environmental protection.

Europe's long-term green and social transition objectives risk being eroded as defence, strategic autonomy, and competitiveness increasingly dominate fiscal priorities. To preserve its commitment to climate neutrality, the EU would need to pursue not only greater policy coherence among its member states but also deeper integration of climate objectives into all dimensions of its policies. Green investment and sustainable funding would have to be firmly embedded within industrial, security, and fiscal strategies under a coherent and transparent framework of budgetary governance. Failing to do so could lead to short-term geopolitical imperatives undermining Europe's long-term sustainability and climate commitments.

A product of SLYCAN Trust November 2025

Organizational profile

SLYCAN Trust is a non-profit think tank working on climate change, sustainable development, climate finance, risk management, entrepreneurship, biodiversity and ecosystem conservation, security, and social justice including gender and youth empowerment. Our work spans the national, regional, and global level from policy analysis and evidence-based research to capacity-building, technical support provision, and on-the-ground implementation.

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